

Biodiversity.be

Highlights Report 2024

Belgian Biodiversity Platform

For Science, Policy and Practice

With the support of BELSPO, Belgian Science Policy Office

FOREWORD

As we reflect on 2024, it is clear that this year has been a pivotal one for biodiversity science-policy in Europe. The urgency of the biodiversity and climate crises has never been more apparent, and in response, the policy and scientific communities have worked more closely than ever to drive forward transformative change.

At the European level, major milestones have shaped the policy landscape. The implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 continued to gain momentum, with new nature restoration commitments and strengthened legal frameworks. The adoption of the Nature Restoration Law, despite challenges, marked a significant step toward reversing ecosystem degradation across the continent. Meanwhile, the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework entered its critical implementation phase, requiring nations to translate global commitments into national and regional action.

In parallel, science has played a crucial role in informing these policy processes. Advances in biodiversity monitoring, enhanced by Earth observation technologies, and citizen science initiatives, have provided policymakers with more precise and timely data. Throughout the year, collaboration has been at the heart of progress. Scientific institutions, policymakers, and stakeholders across sectors have come together in a range of forums, fostering knowledge exchange and co-creation of solutions.

As we move forward, the lessons of 2024 will shape the next phase of biodiversity action at the national, regional and global levels. The need for ambitious, evidence-based policies is greater than ever, and continued collaboration between science and policy will be key to achieving lasting change. With this in mind, in 2024 the Platform continued to strengthen its role as a bridge between knowledge and action. Our 2024 Highlights report showcases an overview of our achievements, including our role hosting the national focal point for key international initiatives (IPBES, IUCN, and GBIF), and as active partners within key European projects (Horizon Europe, LIFE, Biodiversa+).

We sincerely appreciate everyone who has contributed to our activities and achievements and look forward to continued collaboration and action!

Enjoy the read!

Divija Jata
Coordinator

CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION 7

KNOWLEDGE BROKERAGE 9

IPBES focal point	10
IUCN focal point	13
Belgian Presidency of the Council of the EU	15
GBIF National Node	17
Biodiversa +	18
Belgian Biodiversity Alliance	19
Expert committee/Advisory board	20
Communication and Outreach	22
Capacity building	23
Networking and think-tank activities	24

FORESIGHT AND RESEARCH FRAMING 27

Publications	28
Horizon scanning and research prioritisation	29

OPEN EVIDENCE IN SUPPORT OF DECISION MAKING 33

Belgian Delegation for GBIF	34
FAIR and Open Data	34
Diversifying Data Publication	35
Open Evidence	35
Decision Making support tools and systems	35

OUR TEAM 36

PARTNERS 38

Biodiversity.be

Our Mission

Decision-making on biodiversity issues is grounded on sound evidence and takes place through collaboration between actors.

INTRODUCTION

The Belgian Biodiversity Platform (BBPf, referred to as “the Platform”) serves as a science-policy interface, funded by the Belgian Science Policy Office (BELSPO) and is supported by a Cooperation Agreement between federal and concerned federated authorities. Acting as a liaison among policy, science, and practice within the complex field of biodiversity, the Platform addresses various topical issues, including Ecosystems and Society, Biological Invasions, Biodiversity and Climate change, One Health, and Biodiversity Conservation.

Our multidisciplinary team is composed of biodiversity experts, data officers, IT specialists, science-policy officers, and communications officers. The Platform operates across several host institutes based at federal and regional levels within Belgium. These strategic placements ensure robust support for the Platform's mandate and activities.

In 2024, the Platform was more active than ever, organising, co-organising, supporting, and participating in over 50 events that brought together biodiversity science-policy stakeholders across national, European, and international landscapes. Notably, the Platform's participation and inclusion within the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the European Union, and in the organisation of IUCN's Regional Conservation Forum showed the key role it plays for biodiversity and conservation issues.

Gradually entering a new funding phase, the Platform has been reflecting on its niche within the biodiversity science-policy arena and has begun developing a robust and ambitious new strategy for the next five-year phase.

Strategic objective:

To provide capacity and infrastructures on biodiversity science, policy and practice

1

**KNOWLEDGE
BROKERAGE**

IPBES BELGIAN FOCAL POINT

The Belgian Biodiversity Platform serves as National Focal Point for the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services ([IPBES](#)). Established in 2012 by 94 member states, including Belgium, its mission is to assess the state of biodiversity, ecosystems, and their services to society, and bridge the gap between science and policy by providing objective, expert knowledge to inform decision-making at all levels.

Anna Heck, acting as Secondary IPBES National Focal Point (NFP), represents the Platform in this mandate, working in close collaboration with BELSPO, where both the IPBES and the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change ([IPCC](#)) NFPs are coordinated under the leadership of Bart Rymen.

The Platform focuses on operational aspects: engaging Belgian experts in the IPBES work programme, promoting the uptake of deliverables, and co-leading plenary negotiations. It also spearheads the Focal Point in European and international capacity-building activities, positioning Belgium as an active contributor to IPBES and evidence-based policymaking.

Interaction with other national focal points

The Platform continues to exchange best practices with other National Focal Points (NFPs), including during IPBES dialogue meetings, which in 2024 focused on the Nexus and Transformative Change Assessments, the internal and external review of IPBES, and the new policy support function.

The Focal Point also revived an initiative to strengthen collaboration between the IPBES and IPCC NFPs, partnering with the Swiss NFPs, and supported by France and the European Commission.

Informal meetings between NFPs from both bodies allowed for exchanges on ongoing processes, to coordinate strategic efforts, and build a critical mass of countries supporting collaboration. They also discussed upcoming deliverables, meetings, workshops, and expert calls where cross-community involvement could be valuable.

The timing was particularly opportune, as both IPBES and IPCC have entered new cycles under fresh leadership, with their respective timelines - the cycle of the 7th Assessment Report (IPCC AR7) and the IPBES rolling work programme - aligned toward major deliverables in 2028–2029, such as the IPCC AR7 report and the second IPBES Global Assessment.

11th IPBES Plenary

Anna Heck co-led the Belgian Delegation at the eleventh IPBES plenary session in Windhoek, Namibia - the first one held on African soil.

The Belgian Delegation at IPBES-11 in Windhoek. From left to right: Bart Rymen (BELSPO), Catherine Debryune (SPW), Sander Jacobs (INBO), Hilde Eggermont (INBO), Anna Heck (BBPF).
Photo credit: Hilde Eggermont

through the
Intergovernmental
Science-Policy
Platform on
Biodiversity and
Ecosystem Services
(IPBES)

During this plenary, governments adopted two important assessments:

The [Nexus Assessment](#), which provides decision-makers with the scientific evidence on the complex interconnections between these elements and explores more than sixty response options to maximise co-benefits across the nexus.

The [Transformative Change Assessment](#), which explains what transformative change is, how it occurs, and how to accelerate it for a just and sustainable world.

Governments also approved the scoping of the Second Global Assessment. Building on the First Global Assessment (2019), it will incorporate new knowledge on the state of global biodiversity. The assessment process was started, and author selections are scheduled for early 2025.

through the
Intergovernmental
Science-Policy
Platform on
Biodiversity and
Ecosystem Services
(IPBES)

With both IPBES and IPCC NFPs represented by the same person at the Plenary, Belgium reaffirmed its commitment to a stronger collaboration between these two intergovernmental science-policy bodies. Most notably, a new workshop on biodiversity and climate change was approved, as a follow-up to the [workshop held in 2021](#). The outcomes will serve, amongst others, to inform the second global assessment.

Anna Heck, at IPBES-11.
Photo credit: IISD/ENB - Kiara Worth

The ECA network

Finally, the Platform facilitates the [ECA network](#) which brings together NFPs and stakeholders across Europe and Central Asia.

In 2024, the ECA network joined forces with the RESPIN project to co-organise the 8th Pan-European Stakeholder Consultation ([PESC-8](#)) meeting, held every two years. Scheduled for 2025, it will focus on the links between biodiversity and climate change, while connecting the IPBES and IPCC communities from these regions.

IUCN BELGIAN FOCAL POINT

The Platform also plays a pivotal role as the Belgian Focal Point for the International Union for the Conservation of Nature ([IUCN](#)) and performs several strategic functions in the work of the Union.

The IUCN is the world's oldest and largest environmental network, composed of more than 1,300 organisations and 15,000 experts. Belgium currently has [19 IUCN members](#) including governments from all the regions and a strong representation from national NGOs.

The IUCN Regional Conservation Forum

Held every four years, the IUCN Regional Conservation Fora convene its Members, Commissions, and the Secretariat to prepare for the next IUCN World Conservation Congress.

In 2024, the Regional Conservation Forum for Europe, North and Central Asia ([RCF24ENCA](#)) was organised in Bruges by the Platform, under the leadership of Divija Jata (acting as the IUCN Belgian Focal Point), jointly with the IUCN European Regional Office and the IUCN Regional Office for East Europe and Central Asia.

Bringing IUCN constituents from West Europe, and from East Europe, North and Central Asia, the RCF24ENCA was a major opportunity to present their work, their sustainable development issues, and their conservation priorities.

Forum in numbers

- ▶ 400+ attendees in person and online
- ▶ 20% of youth participants
- ▶ Close to 50 countries represented
- ▶ Gender balanced in overall participation and seat at panels
- ▶ 45% of members across Europe, North and Central Asia
- ▶ 58 thematic sessions

through the
International Union
For the Conservation
of Nature (IUCN)

Over three days, the participants engaged in 58 Thematic Sessions, plenary discussions, and a dynamic Forum Fair. Together, they explored pathways to scale up conservation action, integrate equity into natural resource governance, transition to Nature-positive economies, and leverage disruptive innovation for biodiversity protection.

Feedback received from Members through Mentimeter

These discussions contributed significantly to the development of IUCN's 20-year Strategic Vision, together with the intersessional IUCN Programme for the next four years (2026–2029), which will guide global conservation efforts in the years to come.

Group picture at the RCF24ENCA.
Photo credit: [Wim De Wulf / IUCN](#)

"Conversations emphasised the importance of IUCN's evidence-based role and the need to ensure a range of actors, from youth, local communities and Indigenous peoples to the private sector, are part of conservation work."

- Divija Jata, BBPF Coordinator & IUCN Focal Point

You can find more information on the [dedicated webpage](#), and capture the spirit of the event by exploring the [photos taken on site](#).

BELGIAN PRESIDENCY OF THE COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

Belgium, one of the founding members of the European Union, exemplifies the deep-rooted connection to the Union. Situated at the crossroads of Europe, this country has played a key role in the creation and evolution of European cooperation.

The Platform actively supported the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the European Union at different international biodiversity meetings, including:

- Convention on Migratory Species ([CMS COP 14](#)), in Samarkand, Uzbekistan, from 12 to 17 February 2024
- CBD Subsidiary Body for Implementation ([CBD SBI 5](#)), in Cali, Colombia, from 16 to 18 October 2024.

*Divija Jata (center, above) at SBI-5
Photo credit: IISD/ENB - Mike Muzurakis*

*Belgian Delegation at CMS COP 14, with BBPf colleagues Anna Heck and Divija Jata (on the left)
Photo credit: courtesy of an unknown participant*

*Anna Heck (on the right) at CMS COP 14
Photo credit: IISD/ENB - Kiara Worth*

The Platform also supported the Belgian Presidency in the negotiations at the Open-Ended Working Group ([OEWG 3](#)) for a Science-Policy Panel to Contribute Further to the Sound Management of Chemicals and Waste and to Prevent Pollution, in Geneva, Switzerland, from 17 to 21 June 2024. As this new science-policy panel is being modelled after existing panels such as IPBES, the experience of the Platform with regard to governance and implementation was sought to strengthen the delegation.

Belgian Delegation at OEWG3, with colleagues Anna Heck (third from the left) and Nastja Elst (fourth from the left).
Photo credit: IISD/ENB - Mike Muzurakis

Finally, the Platform was also present at the event "[Border controls on Invasive Alien Species](#)" on the 14 March 2024 where Sonia Vanderhoeven presented the result of the 2023 IPBES assessment on Invasive Alien Species and their control.

Minister Zakia Khattabi speaking (on the right), Sonia Vanderhoeven (second from the right), at the event on Border controls on Invasive Species.
Photo credit: ©Isoway.

GBIF NATIONAL NODE

Since 2005, the Platform has been the Belgian Node for the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), an international network of countries and organisations and a research infrastructure, dedicated to providing open access to global biodiversity data about all life on Earth.

As such, it coordinates the community of Belgian data providers and users, facilitates data publication and use through helpdesk, training and maintenance of a variety of tools.

*André Heughebaert showcasing gbif.be at the Be.DiSSCo-FED Networking Event (20 December 2024).
Photo credit: Maxime Coupremanne.*

For more details, see the [annual report of Belgium GBIF activities](#).

A specimen of the superfamily Limacoidea emerging from decaying bark in a humid forest microhabitat, Belgium.
Photo credit: Lise Goudeseune

BIODIVERSA+

[Biodiversa+](#) is the European co-funded biodiversity Partnership supporting excellent research on biodiversity with an impact for policy and society (2021-2028). The Platform, on behalf of the Belgian Science Policy Office (BELSPO), has a central role in Biodiversa+, hosting the two Biodiversa+ Communications Officers, Phong Hoang and Leendert Plaetinck.

One of the main objectives of Biodiversa+ is to produce actionable knowledge to tackle the direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation.

In this context, Biodiversa+ supported projects funded under the BiodivNBS call (focussing on Nature-Based Solutions), and the BiodivTransform Call (on Transformative Change).

Communication and outreach

In 2024, the Platform was responsible for Work Package 6 on communications, playing a crucial role in enhancing the Partnership's visibility and impact.

The two Biodiversa+ Communications Officers oversaw the development and implementation of Biodiversa+'s communications strategy, creating a wide range of materials, including brochures, reports, newsletters, infographics, and presentations.

They also managed Biodiversa+'s social media presence which, in 2024, included the addition of a new platform, [Bluesky](#).

Additionally, the team managed the [Biodiversa+ website](#) and contributed to the development of digital tools such as BioRep and BioAccess, both of which are currently in production.

The [Biodiversa+ databases](#) on research projects and infrastructures were also curated by the Platform.

Mock-up of the BioAccess tool, currently under development.

BiodivHealth policy briefs

through Biodiversa+

In 2024, the Platform played a key role in the production of [three policy briefs for BiodivHealth](#), a Biodiversa+ call focused on the connections between biodiversity and human health, and addressing critical topics of biodiversity and agricultural health, health risk mitigation, and landscape diversity.

Their content is based on high-level scientific findings from BiodivHealth projects, translating complex research into accessible insights for policymakers and stakeholders.

To ensure broad dissemination and engagement, a press release was issued on 5 December 2024 in Brussels, emphasising the key findings and policy recommendations. This initiative aimed to raise awareness of the crucial role biodiversity plays in human and environmental health while supporting evidence-based policymaking.

The three policy briefs on Biodiversity and Health topics, linked to the Biodiversa+ BiodivHealth call.

BELGIAN BIODIVERSITY ALLIANCE

The Belgian Biodiversity Alliance (BBA) is an independent coalition of public and private partners seeking to provide a common platform to showcase concrete contributions from public and private actors in favour of biodiversity in Belgium.

In 2024, the Platform played a central role in the Alliance, with Lennie Plaetinck providing key support to the BBA Secretariat.

This included communication on the Alliance's objectives and progress, logistical coordination of meetings and events, streamlining internal information flows, managing website content, and helping engage with the Alliance partners and the exemplary projects.

EXPERT COMMITTEES & ADVISORY BOARDS

Belgian One Health Network

The Belgian One Health network ([BeOH](#)), coordinated by Dominique Vandekerchove, brings together Belgian One Health actors to enhance collaboration, coordination, capacity building, and communication. It places strong emphasis on a holistic and interdisciplinary approach to One Health issues.

In 2024, Dominique Vandekerchove organised a multidisciplinary workshop on innovation in sensors for water and air quality, attended by 40 experts.

She was also present in several brainstorming and networking opportunities including the Pasteur Network and UNEP meeting (21 February 2024), the BBPf Spring Market (20 March 2024), the 'Paradigm shifts for Global One Health' event (23-25 April 2024), the IUCN Regional Conservation Forum (30 September-2 October 2024), and the Be-cause health General Assembly (10 October 2024).

*Meeting with the Pasteur Network and UNEP at the Groeselenberg site of Sciensano.
Dominique Vandekerchove (on the far right).
Photo credit: Stefan Roels.*

Preventing Zoonotic Disease Emergence

[PREZODE](#)'s objective is to understand the drivers and risk factors associated with zoonotic disease emergence, the underlying ecological and epidemiological mechanisms, and how to detect and mitigate these events as early as possible ('deep prevention').

The PREZODE Belgian Expert Group (BEEG) was created in 2022 with the purpose to work towards a national action plan for deep prevention of zoonotic disease emergence.

In 2024, at the request of the Belgian Ministers of Environment, Health and Agriculture, six BEEG working groups were created to explore the possibilities for implementing the [2023 Policy recommendations](#). The outputs will be used to draft a memorandum by mid-2025.

The whole effort is co-piloted by the FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (Maud Istasse) and the Platform (Dominique Vandekerchove).

BRAIN project steering committee

The [BRAIN-be framework programme](#) integrates several funding initiatives of BELSPO with the aim of stimulating further effective collaborations between the research implemented by the Federal Scientific Institutions (FSIs) and the wider scientific community.

The Platform has been part of the follow-up committees for three BRAIN projects:

- TANGO, a project estimating tipping points in Antarctic benthic ecosystems during future climate change scenarios.
- INTERCEPT, a project monitoring the trade of exotic animals, wild meat, and the pathogens they carry.
- FOURCAST, a project on forests and urban islands' effects on the adaptation of climate and its effects on biodiversity. Leendert Plaetinck attended the follow-up committee meeting on 14 November 2024 at the Royal Meteorological Institute of Belgium.

The Platform consults on these projects, providing support in terms of science-policy interfacing, outreach, stakeholder engagement, and communication.

GBIF CESP 2024 Selection Panel

This year, the Belgian GBIF Node, hosted by the Platform and under the leadership of André Heughebaert, provided support to the GBIF global network by participating in the selection panel of the 2024 [Capacity Enhancement Support Programme](#) (CESP) call. The programme addresses capacity needs of the Participant network and supports the goals of the 2024 Nodes Implementation Plan. The expertise of the Platform on data and the network was put to work to advise and to select proposals to be funded by the programme, under the organisation of the GBIF Secretariat.

COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH

In 2024, the Platform, through the work of Leendert Plaetinck and Ashley Norman, has continued to maintain a strong social media presence, delivering timely updates on biodiversity science-policy topics at the Belgian, European, and international levels. Through these channels, the Platform provides easy access to its activities, fostering engagement with a diverse audience in an informal and interactive online space.

The Platform’s presence on [Facebook](#), [Instagram](#), [LinkedIn](#), and [X](#) kept growing steadily, with an increasing number of followers across all channels, except for X, where the decline aligns with broader trends on that platform.

Social media followers across the four different platforms, and the extra followers the Platform gained during 2024.

@biodiversity.be

@Biodiversity_be

@belgian_biodiversity_platform

Belgian Biodiversity Platform

The [Platform’s website](#) serves as its primary and most comprehensive communications hub. It provides an in-depth overview of who they are, details about their work, information on upcoming events, and much more.

In addition to these efforts, the Platform publishes a monthly newsletter - the [Biodiversity Newsflash](#) - sent to over 3,500 subscribers. This newsletter highlights the latest developments across the different working areas, ensuring its stakeholders stay up to date with key biodiversity initiatives and discussions.

CAPACITY BUILDING

Support to the Croatian GBIF Node

As the well-established Belgian GBIF Node, the Platform notably participated in the [CroMent](#) project, funded under the Capacity Enhancement Support Programme (CESP).

The Platform's contribution included the transfer of knowledge and experience to the newly established Croatian Node, namely through a series of hands-on workshops discussing relevant information from the GBIF secretariat.

From 19 to 23 February 2024, Zagreb hosted a GBIF immersion event (the [CroMent Workshop on biodiversity data and the GBIF network 2024](#)), organised by the Belgian Biodiversity Platform, the Croatian Institute for Environment and Nature, and The Habitat Foundation and aimed at enhancing biodiversity data mobilisation for the new GBIF node in Croatia.

The participants worked intensively in breakout sessions, transforming raw biodiversity data into GBIF-ready datasets. The event facilitated collaboration, addressing key challenges like time constraints, training gaps, and formatting issues. With a strong focus on open science and community-building, the workshop laid the groundwork for a robust GBIF Croatia Node. The results are available on [Belgium's country page](#) and in the [GBIF activity report](#).

The Croatian GBIF has subsequently hosted and organised the annual GBIF ECA nodes meeting from 26 to 29 May 2024 in Zagreb, attended by André Heughebaert, Dimitri Brosens, and Stijn Cooleman.

Black-crowned Night Heron (*Nycticorax nycticorax*), observed during the BioBlitz organised in parallel of the GBIF ECA node in Croatia.
Photo credit: Matt Blissett, [iNaturalist](#), CC BY 4.0

NETWORKING AND THINK TANK ACTIVITIES

Biodiversity Spring Market 2024

The Platform organised its yearly [Biodiversity Spring Market 2024](#), bringing together stakeholders from across Belgium to exchange knowledge, showcase initiatives, and foster collaboration. This year's theme, Nature-Based Solutions, highlighted innovative approaches to integrating biodiversity into environmental and climate strategies.

Speakers of the morning session shared insightful and inspiring presentations discussing regional efforts to promote nature-based solutions, the crucial role of biodiversity in climate resilience and ecosystem restoration, and policy frameworks supporting nature-based solutions.

In the afternoon, the Spring Market created a dynamic and engaging space where participants could discover 22 initiatives from various organisations. The lively atmosphere and strong spirit of collaboration made it an excellent networking opportunity for professionals working on biodiversity and sustainability.

With close to 100 participants, this edition of the Spring Market once again demonstrated the value of bringing together Belgium's biodiversity community to inspire action and strengthen collaboration. Participants left with new insights, connections, and motivation to further advance nature-based solutions in their work.

*Pictures of the Spring Market 2024, taking place at INBO premises, Brussels.
Photo credit: Leendert Plaetnick*

Empowering Biodiversity Research conference

The third edition of the [Empowering Biodiversity Research conference](#) (EBR III) was held on 25 and 26 March 2024 at the [Naturalis Biodiversity Center](#) in Leiden.

Co-organised by the GBIF Nodes of Belgium, the Netherlands, and Luxembourg, this first international edition focused on the power of biodiversity data as a driving force for impactful research and evidence-based policy. Bringing together over 100 participants of scientists, policymakers, research institutions, and infrastructure providers, EBR III offered a dynamic programme featuring cutting-edge talks, interactive discussions, a poster session, and a Biodiversity Informatics market.

The EBR III conference in Leiden.
Photo credit: Maxime Couprenne.

It was a real success regarding the number of participants, the participation of key initiatives on biodiversity informatics of the BENELUX and EU landscape, and in terms of outcomes (see the [Bioengineering article about the EBR conference](#)).

LIFE RIPARIAS Mid-Term Conference

LIFE RIPARIAS organised an [international conference](#) on 10 December 2024. This so-called "mid-term conference" aimed to promote the LIFE RIPARIAS workflow on an international stage, while facilitating exchanges on innovative tools and approaches for managing invasive alien species.

Themed "*Innovative Tools and Approaches for the Management of Biological Invasions*", the event welcomed EU-wide stakeholders involved in the field of biological invasions, including managers, institutional representatives, decision-makers, nature conservation associations, and scientists.

Six talks were delivered by eight renowned international speakers. Sonia Vanderhoeven presented the Life RIPARIAS data workflow from observations to IAS management. This event attracted around 200 national and international participants.

The Platform team at the release of ManalIAS during the LIFE RIPARIAS mid-term conference.
Photo credit: Sonia Vanderhoeven.

Strategic objective:

To facilitate collaboration between regional and federal actors in support of biodiversity science-policy interfacing

2

FORESIGHT AND RESEARCH FRAMING

PUBLICATIONS

In this working area, the Platform contributes to scientific papers, going beyond a simple aid to the presentation of research results. Because of its strong position between science and policy, the Platform witnesses the needs of both communities and actively works to connect them.

In 2024, the team co-wrote four publications:

Reproducible WiSDM: a workflow for reproducible invasive alien species risk maps under climate change scenarios using standardized open data

Davis, A. J. S., Groom, Q., Adriaens, T., **Vanderhoeven, S.**, De Troch, R., Oldoni, D., Desmet, P., Reyserhove, L., Lens, L., & Strubbe, D. (2024). *Reproducible WiSDM: a workflow for reproducible invasive alien species risk maps under climate change scenarios using standardized open data*. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2024.1148895>

This paper presents WiSDM, a reproducible and open-source species distribution modelling workflow for producing IAS risk maps under climate change scenarios.

Curbing the major and growing threats from invasive alien species is urgent and achievable.

Roy, H. E., Pauchard, A., Stoett, P. J., Truong, T. R., Meyerson, (...) **Vanderhoeven, S.**, (...), Ziller, S. R. (2024). *Curbing the major and growing threats from invasive alien species is urgent and achievable*. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 8(7), 1216–1223. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-024-02412-w>

This article outlines the main findings of the IPBES assessment on invasive alien species, presenting clear evidence of the rising global threat of biological invasions and highlighting the urgent need for coordinated action.

An in-depth dataset of northwestern European arthropod life histories and ecological traits

Logghe, G., Batsleer, F., Maes, D., Permentier, T., Berg, M., **Brosens, D.**, **Coleman, S.**, De Smedt, P., Hagge, J., Lambrechts, J., Pollet, M., Verheyde, F., & Bonte, D. (2024). *An in-depth dataset of northwestern European arthropod life histories and ecological traits*. *Biodiversity Data Journal*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.13.e146785>

This study introduces a comprehensive traits dataset for arthropods in northwestern Europe, tailored to support predictive models of species vulnerability under climate and land-use change by including key traits like dispersal ability, thermal niche, and feeding guild.

HORIZON SCANNING AND RESEARCH PRIORITISATION

The RESPIN project

[RESPIN](#) (REinforcing Science-Policy INterfaces for integrated biodiversity and climate knowledge and policies) is a EU-funded project that began in January 2024 and is set to run until 2027. It aims to support the integrated provision and use of IPBES and IPCC processes and outputs.

The Platform, on behalf of BELSPO, is co-leading Function 1 project with its French partner FRB (Foundation for Biodiversity Research). This Function investigates gaps and needs of knowledge holders' participation in IPBES and IPCC processes by characterising their profiles, assessing their level of engagement, and improving existing capacity-building activities. These efforts are designed to strengthen the engagement of underrepresented knowledge holders in IPBES/IPCC processes and foster long-term collaboration.

In 2024, together with FRB, the Platform developed an IPBES and IPCC Engagement survey, conducted through desk studies, questionnaires, and interviews, gathering in total more than 500 responses. The survey, along with several IPBES/IPCC National Focal Points meetings, gave valuable insight into how stakeholders perceive these international processes and what their capacity building needs are. The results will lead to the production of capacity-building pilots for knowledge holders.

The Platform also started the preparations, together with the IPBES ECA Network, for a meeting of IPBES and IPCC communities taking place in Brussels early 2025.

Expertise Registry

As part of a contract between the Platform and the SPW (Service public de Wallonie) on "*A Framework Structuring Biodiversity Research in Support of Decision-Making in Wallonia*", Sonia Vanderhoeven, Lison Cowez, and François Malherbe have developed together an open-access [Expertise Registry](#), available to all stakeholders.

It was created based on a survey distributed to a diverse range of Belgian research units engaged, directly or indirectly, in biodiversity-related fields. The heads of these units were invited to select their research topics from a predefined list of topics and sub-topics developed in 2023.

This Registry is part of the Platform's effort to map and strengthen the biodiversity research community. It helps identify strengths and gaps in knowledge while maintaining an up-to-date record of expertise within the landscape. Currently, the registry provides visibility on the expertise of research units, with individual experts set to be included in 2025.

The Nature-Based Solutions Atlas

The Atlas aims to address the complex social, economic, climatic, and ecological challenges in urbanised areas by showcasing nature-based solutions (NBS) focused on urban water management and greening the built environment. While many local governments are making efforts to implement green-blue infrastructure, information on such interventions is still fragmented and lacks a central overview. The NBS Atlas aims to change this by bringing together inspiring real-world projects and expertise from different domains in a publicly accessible website and a supporting research database. Through this integrated approach, the NBS Atlas aims to bridge gaps between research, policy, and practice, and to promote evidence-based urban planning.

Rozemaipark: the once-enclosed pioneer forest has partly made way for an open, adventurous stream valley with stepping stones. Ekeren, Antwerpen.
Photo credit: [Lucid](#)

The Platform is involved in the development of the NBS Atlas ("[Atlas Groenblauwe Oplossingen](#)") by supporting Ewaut van Wambeke, who is leading this initiative at INBO.

Insight Paper on evidence-based decision-making for biodiversity

Following the [Conservation Research Matters II](#) conference held in December 2023 in Brussels, Sonia Vanderhoeven and Lison Cowez developed an Insight Paper on "[Embracing Evidence: Advancing Biodiversity Decision-making](#)" (available in English, French, and Dutch).

This paper synthesises key discussions, background materials, and keynote presentations from the event. It aims to inform policymakers involved in biodiversity decision-making and stakeholders contributing to scientific data and knowledge, including researchers, citizen scientists, and practitioners. By sharing the insights gained during the conference and from relevant literature, this publication presents the challenges limiting the implementation of evidence-based approaches in Belgium.

Speckled Yellow moth (*Pseudopanthera macularia*), Jalhay, Belgium.
Photo credit: Lise Goudeseune

Strategic objective:

To catalyse innovative approaches which improve the transdisciplinary evidence-base on biodiversity

3

OPEN EVIDENCE in support of decision making

BELGIAN DELEGATION FOR GBIF

The Platform, as Belgian Node for GBIF under the leadership of André Heughebaert, contributes to the regional and global successes of this key Biodiversity Data Infrastructure for Research and Science Policy and continues its recurring collaborations within the GBIF Community, seeking synergies with the IPBES and the CBD National Focal Point.

"We publish the best possible biodiversity data to support research, policy and decisions through a vibrant Belgian network of data publishers"

- André Heughebaert, Belgian Node for GBIF

FAIR AND OPEN DATA

GBIF.be Hosted Portal

In July 2024, the Platform launched the [GBIF.be Hosted Portal](#). This portal hosts all available biodiversity data from Belgium, openly shared through GBIF. It enables users to explore occurrences, datasets, publishers and literature on biodiversity related to Belgium.

Screenshot of the GBIF.be Hosted Portal

Global Registry of Scientific Collections

Another GBIF related portal contribution by the Platform this year was regarding the Global Registry of Scientific Collections ([GRSciColl](#)) aiming to improve the visibility of Belgian Natural History collections.

Through this registry, datasets from different data providers documenting zoological specimens located at the Royal Institute of Natural Sciences ([RBINS](#)) were optimally aggregated in higher taxon collections, in line with the [CETAF-DiSSCo classification guidelines](#).

This aggregation was achieved through networking, reviewing data mapping, and pursuing data consistency. Republishing these datasets not only increased the number of occurrence records available on GBIF, but also integrated hyperlinks to the RBINS Virtual Collections for specific parts, such as moth type specimens, for example: [Occurrence for *Leucoma leptota* Collenette, 1932, holotype collected in Indonesia](#).

DIVERSIFYING DATA PUBLICATION

Metabarcoding Data Toolkit

In October 2024, the pilot [Metabarcoding Data Toolkit](#) (MDT) was launched by GBIF, with the aim to improve the integration of eDNA metabarcoding data. The first two datasets ([dataset 1](#) and [dataset 2](#)) were published by the Platform. Together they cover more than 15000 occurrence records from the Belgian area of the North Sea.

OPEN EVIDENCE

GBIF Alert tool

Building on the open-source tool developed by INBO as part of the LIFE RIPARIAS project and winner of the 2023 GBIF Ebbe Nielsen Challenge, Sébastien Ronveaux and Julien Cigar deployed and customised the [GBIF Alert Tool](#) to meet the specific needs of the ManalIAS project.

ManalIAS required the coverage to include Luxembourg and Ireland, which made it necessary for the Platform to host the system on its servers. The tool was adapted by defining species and zones of interest and by tailoring the interface to better serve field managers and policymakers monitoring the spread of invasive alien species (IAS).

DECISION MAKING SUPPORT TOOLS AND SYSTEMS

The LIFE RIPARIAS project

The fourth year of the European project “Reaching Integrated and Prompt Action in Response to Invasive Alien Species” ([LIFE RIPARIAS](#)) saw the finalisation of technical developments to establish the decision support map tool [ManalIAS](#) by Sonia Vanderhoeven and the Platform's IT team, Sébastien Ronveaux, André Heughebaert, and Julien Cigar.

The tool provides a spatially explicit system to assist program managers and policy makers in establishing priorities for IAS management programs and actions. It was officially released on 10 December 2024 during the LIFE RIPARIAS mid-term conference in Brussels.

The MANAIAS mapping tool showing levels of invasion across different Belgian municipalities.

OUR TEAM

MANAGEMENT TEAM

Dr Aline Van Der Werf
Manager

Divija Jata
Coordinator

COMMUNICATION TEAM

Leendert Plaetinck
Communications Officer

Ashley Norman
Communications Officer

Phong Hoang
Communications Officer

OPEN DATA EXPERTS

Dimitri Brosens
GBIF Node Manager

Maxime Coupremagne
Biodiversity Data Officer

Stijn Cooleman
Biodiversity Data Officer

SCIENCE POLICY
EXPERTS

Dr Sonia Vanderhoeven
Science Officer

Anna Heck
Science-Policy Officer

Dr Dominique Vandekerchove
One Health Science Officer

Lison Cowez
Science-Policy Officer

Ewaut Van Wambeke
Nature-Based Solutions Expert

IT EXPERTS

André Heughebaert
IT Team Coordinator

Francois Malherbe
Developer

Sébastien Ronveaux
IT Expert

Julien Cigar
System Administrator

PARTNERS

BELGIAN SCIENCE POLICY OFFICE

The Belgian Biodiversity Platform is grateful to the Belgian Science Policy Office ([BELSPO](#)) for funding and supporting our work.

We are also thankful to the following organisations for hosting our team in their premises:

The Institute of Natural Sciences ([RBINS](#))

The Research Institute for Nature and Forest ([INBO](#))

The Natural and Agricultural Environmental Studies Department ([DEMNA](#))

[Sciensano](#)

Our Steering Committee is composed of BELSPO, the four host organisations, and members hereunder. We would like to thank all of them for the strategic guidance they provide us with.

Biodiversity.be

©2025 Belgian Biodiversity Platform

©Lise Goudeseune: cover page photo of Riparian vegetation

©Icons purchased on The Noun Project

A report compiled by Lise Goudeseune

Designed by Leendert Plaetinck & Lise Goudeseune

Edited by the Belgian Biodiversity Platform team members

Biodiversity.be